

STRAIN-SOFTENING RESPONSE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES UNDER COMPRESSION

N. Zobeiry*, R. Vaziri, A. Poursartip

Composites Group, Depts. of Materials Eng. and Civil Eng., The University of British Columbia

*Corresponding author (navid@composites.ubc.ca)

Keywords: *laminated composites, damage, strain-softening, compression, failure*

1 Introduction

From both numerical and experimental standpoints, it is very desirable to develop a general methodology that can be used to determine the strain-softening response and characteristic damage properties (e.g. damage initiation strain, fracture energy, size of the damage zone) of composite materials. In the absence of a general methodology, one has to conduct multiple experiments combined with simplifying assumptions regarding the damage behaviour of the material in order to construct a strain-softening curve (e.g. [1]-[2]).

Compared to well-developed tensile experiments for composite materials, compression tests and consequently compressive damage properties have received relatively little attention. The main issue that prevents the development of reliable and easy to reproduce compressive experiments is the buckling and instability of test specimens. Under tension, tests such as over-height compact tension (OCT) [3] are conducted to produce a stable and self-similar damage growth. These tests can be used to study and characterize the damage response of laminated composites.

In recent years, a number of studies have been focused on developing tests for studying the progressive damage propagation of composites under compression. Soutis et al. [4]-[5] investigated the compressive fracture properties of open-hole carbon fibre/epoxy laminates. In their study, however, a self-similar crack growth as a result of progressive damage propagation was not observed.

Moran et al. [6] presented their work on the progressive kink band propagation under compression for an edge-notched unidirectional laminate. Later on, Sivashanker [7]-[9] investigated the progressive damage propagation of both unidirectional and multidirectional edge-notched laminates. Using anti-buckling devices to prevent

out-of-plane movement of specimens, he was able to study the progressive damage behaviour under compression.

In some studies, sandwich panels have been used in order to prevent buckling of composite laminates and produce progressive damage propagation (e.g. [10]-[11]).

In a study by Pinho et al. [12]-[13], compact compression tests on relatively small specimens were conducted. Similar to compact tension (CT), using this geometry, self-similar and progressive damage behaviour was observed in their studies.

In this study, a geometry similar to the compact tension test geometry was considered for compact compression (CC) [14] tests (Fig. 1). The size of this specimen is larger than the specimen considered by Pinho et al. [12]-[13] (110×110 mm compared to 60×65 mm) to allow the damage zone to grow to its final height and achieve a stable and self-similar growth pattern. For these tests, a previously developed approach [14]-[18], based on the digital image correlation technique (DIC), has been utilized to determine the compressive damage properties and strain-softening response of composite laminates. Using the DIC technique, full-field displacement vectors of the specimen surface are measured in each test. Based on the acquired data and using the basic principles of mechanics (equilibrium and compatibility), a family of approximate stress-strain curves and subsequently an average strain-softening constitutive behaviour are obtained. To further study the damage zone in these tests and validate the approach, destructive tests such as sectioning and de-plying were conducted. Using the SEM technique and optical microscopy, images of the damage zone were obtained and various regions identified. In the damage zone, formation of failure slip surfaces consisting of two large delamination surfaces merging with an inclined damage surface was observed as the main failure mechanism.

2 Methodology

In this study, the CC specimen geometry (Fig. 1) is used to produce stable and self-similar crack growth, and the damage zone is analyzed using a previously developed technique [14]-[18]. With the aid of high resolution cameras and the DIC technique, surface images are captured during each test. Using image analysis software packages such as DaVis [19] these images are then analyzed and the displacement vectors for virtual nodes on the specimen surface are measured. Surface strains are then calculated based on the measured displacement vectors. Using the strain field and finite element (FE) equations, equilibrium conditions are checked on the specimen surface to determine the boundary separating the damage zone from the undamaged zone at each stage of the test. Afterward, using the elastic stress distribution on the damage zone boundary, an approximate stress distribution inside the damage zone is obtained. Finally, by minimizing local and global cost (objective) functions, an optimized form of the constitutive response of composite laminates is obtained.

To validate the results, both numerical simulations and destructive tests such as de-plying and sectioning are conducted. Experimental and numerical studies are discussed next.

3 Experimental and Numerical Studies

The material used for compact compression (CC) tests was IM7/8552 carbon-epoxy composite panels with a quasi-isotropic lay-up of [90/45/0/-45]_{4S}. To conduct CC tests, a testing fixture was built and utilized in this study. The current compressive jig is shown in Fig. 2. Load is applied through small balls on top and bottom of the jig and transferred to the specimen through the pins near the notch tip. The whole fixture moves inside railing guides around it to prevent buckling and bending of the specimen. During the experiments, out-of-plane displacement was monitored using the DIC technique and no out-of-plane bending was observed. In each test, along with the load data, the pin-opening-displacement (POD) was also recorded using an extensometer fixed between the two pins.

Under displacement controlled condition, several CC tests were conducted. The load-POD

curves of two of the tests are shown in Fig. 3. During each test, displacement fields on the surface of the specimen were obtained using the DIC technique. As described here, using a previously developed methodology [14]-[18], damage related parameters and stress-strain response of the laminate under compression were obtained. Two examples of approximate stress-strain responses obtained from this process are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** Fig. 4 for cross sections at distances of 1.2 mm and 11 mm ahead of the notch tip in the CC specimen, respectively. By overlaying all these curves, the optimized strain-softening response can be constructed as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. The key parameters for the construction of this stress-strain curve and their values are presented in Fig. 6 and Table 1, respectively.

To validate the optimized constitutive response obtained here, independent FE simulations of CC tests were carried out. The LS-DYNA FE code together with its built-in material model, MAT_081, was used to simulate the CC tests. The optimized strain-softening response was used as an input curve for the simulations. The crack band scaling law [20] was applied to adjust the stress-strain curve and thus maintain the objectivity of the numerical results. The load-displacement curve obtained from the LS-DYNA simulation is shown in Fig. 7 along with the results obtained from experiments.

To further study the damage zone, destructive tests were conducted on the damaged samples. Some of the specimens were de-plyed [21] to study the extent of fibre breakage in each ply.

For de-plying, a section of interest in front of the notch was cut from the CC specimens. This section was left in the oven for about 6.5 hours at 420 °C to burn-off most of the epoxy resin. The individual plies were then separated and studied to identify fibre breakage/bending traces in each ply. These traces are shown in Fig. 8, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10.

To further study the damage zone, some specimens were sectioned and analyzed using the SEM technique. Examples of the SEM images are shown in Fig. 11 **Error! Reference source not found.** In Fig. 12 and **Error! Reference source not found.** cross-sectional images along with the schematics of the damage pattern are shown.

4 Results and Discussions

The reasonable agreement between the numerical and experimental results for the load-POD curves (Fig. 7) supports the validity of the obtained strain-softening curve as a representative compressive constitutive response for the composite laminate. It can be observed that the optimized strain-softening response consists of a softening curve followed by a plateau stress before the ultimate failure (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6).

When fibers bend or break under compression, load can still be transferred through the damage zone via friction or other mechanisms before the two damage surfaces start to slide past each other. To examine this conjecture, an optical microscope was used to analyze the tip of the crack on the de-plyed layers. Fig. 10 shows images obtained using an optical microscope for layer #7 (0°) of a CC specimen. From this image we can observe that for the damage area away from the tip of the crack (Fig. 10c), debris and rubble form due to sliding and crushing of fibers on each other. On the other hand, at the tip of the crack (Fig. 10d) there is no indication of such rubble formation.

From the SEM images of the cross-sections (Fig. 11 and **Error! Reference source not found.**), kinking in the 0° layers, off-axis matrix cracking, off-axis fibre breakage/bending, and delamination can be observed as the main failure mechanisms. Based on the obtained strain-softening response and by correlating the cross-sectional images to this curve, the compressive damage zone can be divided into 4 zones as shown in Fig. 13: undamaged zone, softening zone, broadening zone and zero-stress zone. These zones are described below:

- I. Undamaged elastic zone.
- II. Softening zone: In this zone, the damage height increases to a characteristic size. Due to the formation of slip surfaces and excessive fibre breakage/bending, the material loses its load bearing capacity and its modulus decreases significantly.
- III. Broadening zone: Upon applying further compression, damage propagates into the

neighbouring undamaged material. As a result, the damage height increases to a maximum height. A constant stress, or plateau stress, is transferred through this zone.

- IV. Zero stress zone: The two surfaces of the damage slide on each other and the material fails.

In the softening zone and the broadening zone, formation of failure slip surfaces can be observed. These surfaces consist of two large delamination/splitting surfaces merging with an inclined damage surface between them (Fig. 12, **Error! Reference source not found.** and Fig. 13). These surfaces result in a mechanism that reduces the load-bearing capacity of the section noticeably and eventually the two surfaces of the damage slide on each other leading to material failure.

As mentioned earlier, the noticeable difference between the damage behaviour under tension and compression is that the process zone under compression (zones II and III), contains visible fibre breakage/bending. These damaged fibers can still transfer load under compression through friction. Under tension, however, fibre breakage leads to complete loss of load bearing capacity and broken fibers cannot transfer load anymore [22].

5 Summary and Conclusions

In this paper, experimental and numerical results obtained from compact compression tests are presented. The strain-softening response obtained from the CC tests was validated using numerical simulation and destructive testing. The results obtained here highlight the differences between the damage propagation in laminated composites under compression and tension. Under compression, while damage is propagating, load is still being transferred through the zone that contains fibre breakage/bending via friction and other mechanisms. However, under tension, when fibre breakage occurs, load cannot be transferred through the damage zone.

During compressive failure, the composite laminate goes through the softening and broadening steps before the ultimate failure due to the formation of slip surfaces.

The proposed methodology provides insight into the details of damage propagation in composite materials under compression. Moreover, various failure mechanisms can be identified and the differences between tensile and compressive damage propagation can be observed.

References

- [1] N. Zobeiry, A. Forghani, C. McGregor, R. Vaziri, A. Poursartip, "Progressive damage modeling of composite materials under both tensile and compressive loading regimes". *Mechanical Response of Composites, Series: Computational Methods in Applied Sciences*, Springer, 10:179-195, 2008.
- [2] C. McGregor, N. Zobeiry, R. Vaziri, A. Poursartip, "A constitutive model for progressive compressive failure of composites". *J. Composite Mater.*, 42:2687- 2716, 2008.
- [3] I. Kongshavn and A. Poursartip, "Experimental investigation of a strain-softening approach to predicting failure in notched fibre-reinforced composite laminates". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 59, pp. 29-40, 1999.
- [4] C. Soutis, C., P.T. Curtis, N.A. Fleck, "Compressive failure of notched carbon-fibre composites", *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, Vol. 440, No. 1909, pp. 241-256, 1993.
- [5] C. Soutis, J. Lee, C. Kong, C., "Size effect on compressive strength of T300/924C carbon fibre-epoxy laminates", *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, Vol. 31, No. 8, pp. 364-370, 2002.
- [6] P.M. Moran, X.H. Liu, C.F. Shih, "Kink band formation and band broadening in fibre composites under compressive loading", *Acta Metallurgica et Materialia*, Vol. 43, No. 8, pp. 2943-2958, 1995.
- [7] S. Sivashanker, "Damage growth in carbon fibre-PEEK unidirectional composites under compression", *Proceedings of the 1997 Symposium on Integrated Experimental-Computational Modeling of Advanced Materials, McNu'97*, Vol. A249, No. 1-2, pp. 259-276, 1998.
- [8] S. Sivashanker, "Damage propagation in multidirectional composites subjected to compressive loading", *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A: Physical Metallurgy and Materials Science*, Vol. 32, No. 1, pp. 171-182, 2001.
- [9] S. Sivashanker, A. Bag, "Kink-band propagation in a multidirectional carbon fibre-polymer composite", *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A: Physical Metallurgy and Materials Science Physical*, Vol. 32, No. 12, pp. 3157-3160, 2001.
- [10] J. Bayldon, Z.P. Bazant, I.M. Daniel, Q. Yu, "Size effect on compressive strength of sandwich panels with fracture of woven laminate facesheet", *Transactions of the ASME. Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, vol. 128, pp. 169-174, 2006.
- [11] J. Ratcliffe, W. Jackson, J. Schaff, J., "Compression strength prediction of impact-damaged composite sandwich panels", in *60th Annual Forum Proceedings - American Helicopter Society*, pp. 656-672, 2004.
- [12] S.T. Pinho, "Modelling failure of laminated composites using physically-based failure models", PhD Thesis, Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College, London, 2005.
- [13] S.T. Pinho, P. Robinson, L. Iannucci, "Fracture toughness of the tensile and compressive fibre failure modes in laminated composites", *Composites science and technology*, vol. 66, pp. 2069-2079, 2006.
- [14] N. Zobeiry "Extracting the strain-softening response of composites using full-field displacement measurement". Ph.D. Thesis, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada, 2010.
- [15] A. Forghani, N. Zobeiry, A. Poursartip, R. Vaziri, "A Structural Modelling Framework for Prediction of Damage Development and Failure of Composite Laminates", *Journal of Composite Materials*, DOI: 10.1177/0021998312474044, 2013.
- [16] N. Zobeiry, A. Forghani, R. Vaziri, A. Poursartip, "Analyzing the Damage Behaviour of Composites using Full-Field Displacement Measurement. Proceedings of ASC/CANCOM Conference in Montreal, Canada, 2011.
- [17] A. Forghani, N. Zobeiry, R. Vaziri, A. Poursartip, F. Ellyin, "A non-local approach to simulation of damage in laminated composites". *Proceedings of ASC/CANCOM Conference in Montreal, Canada*, 2011.
- [18] N. Zobeiry, A. Forghani, R. Vaziri, A. Poursartip, "A combined experimental and numerical approach for simulating the damage behaviour of notched composite laminates". *Proceedings of ICCM18 conference in Korea*, 2011.

- [19] LaVision. Davis manual-LaVision strain master brochure, www.lavision.de, 2007.
- [20] Z.P. Bazant, B.H. Oh, "Crack Band Theory for Fracture of Concrete", *Materiaux Et Constructions*, vol. 16, pp. 155-177, 1983.
- [21] S.M. Freeman, "Characterization of lamina and interlaminar damage in Graphite/Epoxy composites by the deply technique", 6th Conference of Composite Materials: Testing and Design, pp. 50-62, 1982.
- [22] N. Zobeiry, "Progressive damage modelling of composite materials under compressive loads", MASc. Thesis, Department of Civil Engineering, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, 2004.

Fig. 1. Compact compression (CC) specimen geometry.

Fig. 2. Compact compression (CC) test fixture.

Fig. 3. Load-POD curves for CC tests.

Fig. 4. Approximate compressive stress-strain response obtained 11 mm ahead of the initial notch tip in a CC test.

Fig. 5. Approximate and optimized strain-softening responses under compression.

Fig. 6. Optimized compressive response obtained using the proposed methodology.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the load-POD curves obtained from LS-DYNA and experiments.

Fig. 8. Fibre breakage/bending trace in ply #22 (0°) of the CC specimen for a 43×32 mm cut.

Fig. 9. Fibre breakage/bending trace in ply #4 (45°) of the CC specimen for a 43×32 mm cut.

Fig. 11. Damage zone under compression. Failure mechanisms are kinking (A), off axis matrix cracking and fibre breakage/bending (B), and delamination (C).

Fig. 10. (a) Fibre breakage/bending traces in layer #22 (0°) of CCB1 specimen, (b) showing part of the damage tip, (c) part of the damage zone that still can transfer load under compression and (d) rubble formation leading to loss of load bearing capacity.

Fig. 12. Formation of slip surfaces in cross-sections of the CC specimen at: (a) 27 mm ahead of the initial notch tip with maximum strain equal to -0.7%, (b) 25 mm ahead of the initial notch tip with maximum strain equal to -0.9%, (c) 23 mm ahead of the initial notch tip with maximum strain equal to -1.2%.

Fig. 13. Formation of damage zone under compression.

Table 1. Parameters of the optimized strain-softening response obtained using the proposed methodology.

Elastic modulus	E_x	54.2	(GPa)
	E_y	54.2	(GPa)
Poisson's ratio	ν_{xy}	0.32	
Shear modulus	G_{xy}	20.5	(GPa)
Damage initiation strain	ϵ_i	-1.2%	
Damage saturation strain	ϵ_s	-2.0%	
Ultimate strain	ϵ_u	-4.5%	
Plateau stress	$\sigma_{plateau}$	-200	(MPa)
Total Fracture energy	G_f	85	kJ/m^2